

IRREGULAR WAVE OVERTOPPING OF SEAWALLS

John P. Ahrens and Martha S. Heimbaugh

Coastal Engineering Research Center
U.S. Army Engineer Waterways Experiment Station
Vicksburg, Mississippi

ABSTRACT

This paper discusses recent laboratory tests of irregular wave overtopping of coastal structures being conducted at the Coastal Engineering Research Center (CERC). Current model tests of seawalls has led to an improved method for predicting wave overtopping rates. Structures tested included seawalls fronted by a variety of riprap revetment configurations as well as a seawall with no fronting revetment. Overtopping rates have been found to be strongly dependent on a dimensionless parameter, F' , which is the ratio of the freeboard of the seawall to a measure of the severity of the incident waves. The parameter, F' , contains several variables including the crest elevation of the seawall, the local water level and depth, the zero-moment wave height, and the period of peak energy density of the wave spectrum. A simple exponential model incorporating F' is useful for evaluating and comparing the performance of various seawall/revetment configurations and can be used to compute realistic wave overtopping rates.

INTRODUCTION

Wave runup and overtopping are two of the most important factors influencing the design of coastal structures. Current methods to predict overtopping rates, such as given in the Shore Protection Manual (SPM, 1984), rely on a data base composed primarily of laboratory tests using monochromatic waves. In addition, problems arise in using the SPM overtopping method because of the ambiguity in choosing the proper overtopping coefficients and because of complications related to treating wave runup as an independent variable. Studies have been conducted which indicate that the SPM method can for some circumstances under predict overtopping rates, Douglass (1984) and for other circumstances greatly over predict the overtopping rates, Gadd, et al. (1985). It is not clear when overestimates or underestimates of overtopping rates might be expected. This paper discusses laboratory tests conducted at the U.S. Army Engineer Waterways Experiment Station's (WES) Coastal Engineering Research Center (CERC), Vicksburg, MS. to determine irregular wave overtopping rates for a number of seawall/revetment configurations related to flooding at Roughans Point, MA. This study was initiated to solve a site specific

problem but it has evolved into a more general research investigation with the intention to develop a method to determine irregular wave overtopping rates better than the current method given in the SPM.

BACKGROUND

The current method given in the SPM to calculate overtopping rates is based on small-scale and large-scale laboratory tests using monochromatic waves, Saville (1955). This method requires estimating a potential runup on a hypothetically extended slope as shown in Figure 1. Overtopping rates are calculated by the equation

$$Q = (gQ_o^* H_o')^{1/2} \exp \left[\frac{-0.1085}{\alpha} \ln \left(\frac{R+h-d_s}{R+h+d_s} \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where Q is the overtopping rate per unit length of structure, g is the acceleration of gravity, H_o' is the unrefracted deepwater wave height, R is the potential runup height measured vertically from the still water level on a hypothetically extended slope, h is the crest height of the structure above the seabed, d_s is the water depth at the toe of the structure, and Q_o^* and α are dimensionless overtopping coefficients. Equation 1 can be simplified using some algebra and noting that the freeboard of the structure, F , is defined

$$F = h - d_s .$$

Equation 1 can be simplified to

$$Q = \left(gQ_o^* H_o'^3 \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{R - F}{R + F} \right)^{0.1085/\alpha} \quad (2)$$

for $R > F$

Even in the simplified form of Equation 2 there are a number of problems related to using the SPM method to calculate overtopping rates. One problem is that the method was developed solely on the basis of laboratory tests using monochromatic waves, Saville (1955). The SPM method was developed by Weggel (1976) to help summarize Saville's data and to organize the information into a systematic procedure to calculate overtopping rates. Ahrens (1977) modified Weggel's approach to

Figure 1. Definition sketch of potential runup and overtopping

account for irregular wave conditions but a number of plausible but unproven assumptions were necessary to make this modification; see Douglass (1986) for a discussion of the implications of Ahrens' assumptions. Another problem in using Equation 2 is the overtopping coefficients Q_o^* and α are functions of both the structure configuration and wave conditions. This characteristic of the coefficients makes it difficult to determine the proper values to use for most situations. Weggel (1976) discusses the physical meaning of the coefficients and gives guidance on how to choose their value. Douglass provides a method for interpolating to obtain overtopping rates for conditions which do not coincide with observed values of the coefficients. A third problem with using Equation 2 relates to determining a reasonable value for the potential runup. For simple structure configurations, such as shown in Figure 1, it should not be too difficult to obtain a reasonable value for the potential runup. However, for most real situations which do not have simple geometry it can be quite difficult to determine a reasonable value of the potential runup and for a recurved seawall, the concept of potential runup cannot be clearly defined. Gadd, et al. (1985) found that much of the error associated with using the SPM overtopping method was due to the inability to make good estimates of the potential runup.

In recent years the New England Division of the Corps of Engineers has been considering a number of methods to alleviate coastal flooding due to wave overtopping in a small community just north of Boston, Ma. called Roughans Point, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (1982, 1983). The basic plan was to build a riprap revetment in front of an existing seawall to reduce overtopping rates. Modifications to the basic plan were to be considered if they could be shown to be more effective. However, because of the limitations noted above it was clear that it would be impossible to

make detailed evaluations of the potential effectiveness of various seawall/revetment configurations without laboratory tests of irregular wave overtopping.

TEST CONDITIONS

Laboratory tests were conducted in CERC's 45.73 m long, 0.91 m wide, and 0.91 m deep wave tank. The tank is equipped with a hydraulically actuated, piston type wave maker which is computer controlled. Water depths at the wave maker ranged from 59 to 66 cm and water depths at the toe of the seawall ranged from 14 to 21 cm. The offshore slope in front of the structures tested was 1 on 100 (vertical on horizontal). A JONSWAP type spectrum was produced in the deep part of the tank but because of the extensive wave shoaling and breaking between the wave generator and the structure, the spectrum was considerably wider than a typical JONSWAP at the structure site. The period of peak energy density of the spectrum, T_p , ranged from 1.25 to 3.00 seconds and the incident zero-moment wave heights near the structure ranged from 5 to 17 cm. A 1:16 (model : prototype) undistorted Froude scale was used. Wave conditions were measured using parallel wire resistance type gages. Incident wave conditions were measured in a wave absorber channel parallel to the channel containing the seawall/revetment structure. Details relating to the test setup, procedures, and conditions are given in Ahrens, Heimbaugh, and Davidson (1986).

IMPORTANT FINDINGS

Improved Overtopping Method

One of the most important findings to date is the development of a dimensionless freeboard parameter, F' , which is able to consolidate all the data for one structure configuration into a single well defined trend. The term F' is defined:

$$F' = \frac{F}{\left(\frac{H_{mo}^2}{L_p}\right)^{1/3}} \quad (3)$$

where L_p is the Airy wave length calculated using T_p and the water depth near the toe of the structure. Equation 3 can be thought of as the ratio of the freeboard to the severity of the local, incident wave conditions. A very valuable characteristic of the freeboard parameter is that it combines a lot of information about the structure, water depth, and wave conditions into one variable. The parameter F' has higher correlation with the overtopping rate for the data of this study than any other parameter which could be identified, including the parameter F/H_{mo} , suggested by the work of Goda (1969) and Seelig (1980) or the dimensionless freeboard parameter $F/(T_z g H_s)$ used by Owen (1983), where T_z is the zero-crossing wave period and H_s is the significant wave height of the spectrum. Figure 2 shows a plot of the overtopping rate as a function of F' for the existing seawall configuration at Roughans Point without a riprap revetment protecting the wall. Considering the complexity of the irregular wave overtopping process the ability of F' to consolidate the overtopping data into a well defined trend is surprising.

A simple exponential model using F' was found to be very useful for evaluating the overtopping performance of a seawall/revetment configuration or for comparing the performance of two or more configurations. The model can be written

$$Q = Q_0 \exp(C_1 F') \quad (4)$$

where Q_0 is a coefficient with the same units as the overtopping rate, i.e., volume per unit time per unit length of seawall crest, and C_1 is a dimensionless coefficient. Both Q_0 and C_1 are determined by the data for a particular seawall/revetment configuration either by regression analysis or occasionally by subjective curve fitting, if that seemed more appropriate. A regression curve fit to the data using Equation 4 is shown in Figure 2. Since a regression equation of the form of Equation 4 tends to reduce the influence of the conditions with high overtopping rates, as compared to a linear equation, it was sometimes convenient to subjectively fit an equation of the form of Equation 4 to obtain a better fit to the data having high overtopping rates. In Figure 3 a comparison is shown between a regression curve and a subjectively fit curve for a seawall with a 1.9 cm cap fronted by a revetment with a berm. In Figure 3 the non-regression curve fits the data with high overtopping rates better than the regression curve. For many configurations the regression curves seem quite satisfactory but for some cases, a non-regression curve provides a more conservative trend which would be preferable for design purposes. Possibly a more suitable approach would be to use an equation with the form of Equation 4 with a weight function proportional to either the overtopping rate or F' . In any event the form of Equation 4 fits the data well

and is similar to the form used by Owen (1983) in a study on irregular wave overtopping of sea dikes. Data trend curves of the form of Equation 4 provide a simple way to evaluate the effectiveness of various seawall/revetment configurations, e.g., the less area under the curve the more effective the configuration is at reducing overtopping.

To help keep track of the various seawall/revetment configurations discussed in this paper, a table was prepared giving the configuration number and a brief description. Configuration numbers are consistent with those given in Ahrens, Heimbaugh and Davidson (1986). Table 1 also gives the value of the overtopping coefficients used to make comparisons between and among configurations. This paper will discuss 5 of the 10 configurations tested.

Methods To Reduce Wave Overtopping

One method to reduce wave overtopping is the use of a recurved wall instead of a vertical wall. The Roughans Point seawall is vertical with a small recurve at the crest. Observations indicate that the recurve is effective when the waves are small enough and the water depth at the wall great enough to allow a reasonably coherent standing wave system to be established. This system causes a vertical flow regime at the wall which is thrown seaward by the recurve. The recurve is not effective when the crest height of the incident wave approaches the elevation of the crest of the seawall since the wave simply will inundate the wall spilling large quantities of water over the wall. For the inundation mode it is difficult to envision how any surface feature of the wall could be very effective in reducing the overtopping rate. For tests conducted in this study, the inundation mode of overtopping occurred frequently when F' was less than 0.3. Thus, comparisons of the data trends for F' less than 0.3 were not made.

Data for a vertical wall has been collected but not analyzed at this time (June 1986). When analyzed, it will be compared to data for the recurved wall such as shown in Figure 2. It should be noted that Equation 4 does not take into account water blown over the wall by onshore winds which are usually present during overtopping conditions. Therefore, a recurve which throws water seaward and possibly even downward will control overtopping better than a vertical wall that throws the water straight upward.

A second method to reduce wave overtopping rates is the use of rubble in front of the wall. The purpose of the rubble might be toe protection but if enough rubble is used the dissipation of wave energy will be sufficient to reduce wave overtopping. During this study a standard, multi-layered riprap revetment was built against the seawall with the top of the revetment near the top of the wall just below the recurve. The revetment reduced the overtopping rates by about 45 percent over the same seawall configuration without a revetment. Figure 4 shows a comparison of the

Figure 2. Overtopping rate vs relative freeboard for Roughans Point Seawall with no revetment

Figure 3. Overtopping rate vs relative freeboard for Roughans Point seawall with a revetment and a 1 foot cap

Table 1. List of Various Seawall Revetment Configurations

Configuration No.	Description	Overtopping Coefficients	
		$Q_o \left(\frac{m^3}{m, sec} \right)$	C_1
1	Seawall with no fronting revetment	7.11	-14.08*
2	Seawall fronted by a standard riprap revetment	2.84	-13.43*
4	Seawall fronted by a wide berm, absorber revetment	40.83	-21.62**
7	Seawall fronted by a wide berm, absorber revetment, cap on wall	28.43	-23.07**
8	Seawall fronted by a wide berm, absorber revetment, double cap on wall	8.65	-22.15*

* Coefficients determined by regression analysis.

** Coefficients determined by subjective curve fitting.

Figure 4. Comparison of data trends for the Roughans Point seawall with no fronting revetment (Configuration 1) after the same seawall fronted by a standard riprap revetment (Configuration 2)

performance of the two configurations using data trend curves developed from regression analysis. The figure illustrates the value of the overtopping model discussed above for evaluating the performance of a configuration and making comparisons between configurations. It had been hoped that a standard riprap revetment would be more effective at reducing overtopping than was actually observed. Two possible reasons for the disappointing performance of the riprap were identified: 1) when the water levels are high waves ride over most of the revetment without much attenuation and 2) when water levels are low the standard revetment provides a ramp for waves to ride up and over the wall without encountering a major discontinuity to their flow. The second factor suggested that it might be better to not build the revetment so high against the wall and to use a profile having a berm. This type of profile would provide a major discontinuity at the wall to disrupt the wave action and runup flow and still allow the recurve to be effective. It was also felt that it would be better to build the revetment more like a wave absorber rather than using the standard riprap revetment design. The absorber revetment design would use additional armor stone out near the toe to trip the waves and dissipate the energy as far offshore as possible. These concepts led to the design of a wide berm profile, wave absorber revetment.

The performance of the wide berm, absorber revetment (Configuration 4) in reducing wave overtopping of the seawall can be evaluated using Figure 5. In Figure 5, regression curves are used to compare the overtopping trends for a seawall fronted by a traditional riprap revetment (Configuration 2) to the trend for the seawall fronted by the wide berm, absorber revetment. It can be seen over most of the range of interest the wide berm configuration was better than the standard riprap revetment. In general it appears that a berm located near the mean water level is effective in disrupting the wave action near the seawall and in reducing the overtopping rates. This finding is consistent with conclusions reached by Owen (1983) based on laboratory tests of irregular wave overtopping of sea dikes.

A fourth method to reduce wave overtopping is to increase the crest elevation of the seawall. Because overtopping rates increase approximately exponentially with freeboard the value of increasing the height of the wall can be readily appreciated. Tests were conducted using a 1.9 cm cap and a 3.8 cm cap on the seawall which are referred to as a cap and double cap, respectively. Caps were found to be very effective in reducing overtopping rates. Figure 6 shows overtopping trends for four seawall/revetment configurations including Configuration 7 with a cap and Configuration 8 with a double cap. Configurations 4, 7, and 8 all have the same wide berm, absorber revetment profile so the effectiveness of a cap can be easily evaluated in Figure 6 by comparing the overtopping curves. Although in many situations increasing the height of a seawall would be unexceptionable, Figure 6 shows that the effectiveness of a cap can be equivalent

to placing a great amount of stone in front of the seawall.

SUMMARY

The most important result from this study to date has been the development of an improved wave overtopping model. This model yields a method to calculate irregular wave overtopping rates which has been calibrated through the use of model tests to a number of seawall/revetment configurations. This method has a number of advantages over the current method of computing irregular wave overtopping rates given in the Shore Protection Manual (SPM, 1984). These advantages include: (a) The method is simple, (b) The method does not use the runup or potential runup to compute overtopping rates, (c) The overtopping coefficients are not a function of the wave conditions, (d) The method provides a simple way to compare and rank the effectiveness of various structural configurations in reducing wave overtopping, and (e) It is easy to incorporate the method into computer models to calculate the probability of coastal flooding due to overtopping, see Hardy and Crawford (1986). It is also believed that this new method is more accurate than the SPM method because it was developed directly from irregular wave conditions rather than being adapted from monochromatic wave overtopping tests.

Using laboratory tests and the new overtopping model a number of strategies for reducing wave overtopping of coastal structures, are being investigated and evaluated. These strategies include: the use of a recurve on a seawall, the use of a standard riprap revetment fronting a seawall, the use of a wide berm type of revetment profile fronting the seawall, and the use of a cap on the seawall to increase the height of the wall.

Additional seawall/revetment configurations are being tested. These tests will provide a way to calculate irregular wave overtopping rates for a number of promising seawall/revetment configurations. It is also intended to generalize and refine the new overtopping model so that more accurate estimates of overtopping rates can be made and so that the model better reflects the physical process involved.

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Figure 5. Comparison of data trends for the Roughans Point seawall fronted by a standard riprap revetment (Configuration 2) and the same seawall fronted by a wide berm, absorber revetment (Configuration 4)

Figure 6. Overtopping trends for Configurations 1, 4, 7, and 8.